

D4.5: Updated plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities (DEPC)

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ABSTRACT:	<p>POIESIS is heavily dependent on the quality of dissemination, exploitation and communication, since those types of activities are essential for spreading information about the progress of the project, the events organized and the main findings and other outcomes. This does not only create visibility for the project's findings but also facilitates the recruitment for the engagement activities foreseen by POIESIS workplan. POIESIS can only be considered a successful project if the envisioned impact is achieved. This, in turn, strongly depends on the extent to which its communications are picked up and implemented by our specific stakeholder groups, as described at the DoA document. The consortium has constructed the following three-stage communication strategy, to be executed within WP4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A preparatory stage mainly employing social media to generate attention to the subject and the project's aims and objectives and the
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	<p>construction of a user-friendly website that outlines the project and provide regular updates of the progress of the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination towards relevant stakeholders at an organisational and individual level for awareness of the upcoming POIESIS outcomes • Delivery of the POIESIS recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research through the project's website. <p>This report presents the update of the DEPC of POIESIS that was submitted M4 of the project. This report is an augmented version of D4.2, based on the interactions with various stakeholders that took place within the first 22 months of POIESIS, in the context of dissemination and communication, as well as in the context of the engagement procedures and empirical data collection studies that were successfully implemented.</p>
Keyword List:	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation.

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	AU	Denmark
2.	Partner	WISSENSCHAFT IM DIALOG GGMBH	WiD	Germany
3.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
4.	Partner	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA	ISCTE	Portugal
5.	Partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS	France
6.	Partner	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	Spain
7.	Associated partner	LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND POLITICALSCIENCE	LSE	UK

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1 Introduction

1.1 The POIESIS project

In a context where societal dependence on sound scientific research and responsible innovation has become increasingly visible, concerns about public trust and mistrust in science have simultaneously been mounting. Pressing global and local challenges cannot be adequately addressed without reliance on valid evidence and innovation uptake. Hence, the cultural authority of science, research, and innovation – the confidence and trust that citizens and societal actors place in science, research, and innovation – is of crucial importance. The project, entitled “Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science” (POIESIS), will systematically develop a knowledge base about trust in science, including detailed examination of how patterns of trust relate to the alignment of research practices with fundamental principles of research integrity on the one hand and the integration of citizens and societal actors in research practices on the other hand.

POIESIS is concerned with the creation or making of knowledge in responsible ways as well as with the consequences in stages of knowledge utilisation, verification and adoption. We examine research integrity and societal integration as prominent vehicles for responsible knowledge creation. We recognize the obvious intrinsic value of conducting research in accordance with appropriate ethical, legal, and professional frameworks, obligations, and standards on the one hand and with the integration of relevant societal stakeholders in all phases of the research cycle on the other hand. However, we tailor our conceptual and empirical research programme to focus specifically on the impact of such responsible (or irresponsible) research practices in terms of societal trust. Our intention is to systematically examine the impact of research integrity and society’s integration in research on societal trust in research and innovation.

The overarching research objective of POIESIS is to understand how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle. Moreover, the project aims to understand how institutions, particularly Research Performing and Research Funding Organisations, can foster research practices that are, in turn, conducive to enhancing public trust in science. Our goal is to develop evidence-based recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research; ultimately contributing in the long-term perspective to increased public trust in science and increased alignment of research with societal needs, expectations, and values.

The evidence-base produced by the project will enable us to contribute to the following specific objectives:

1. To provide recommendations for policy makers, research funding and performing organisations, higher education institutions and other R&I actors for tackling societal mistrust in science, research and innovation;
2. To provide recommendations to research performing and funding organisations, for strengthening the co-creation of research and innovation contents by society, and for the spreading of good practices and evidence of their effects; and
3. To implement innovative means of communicating and disseminating the findings and messages of our research.

A core set of general recommendations, relevant for all end-users, will be extended by sets of user-specific recommendations tailored to their needs. All POIESIS recommendations will be packaged together in an accessible and attractive format, tailored to the specific needs of diverse actors, thereby promoting mutual understanding among Research and Innovation stakeholders.

1.2 Maximising impact

The POIESIS project has developed a plan that revolves around four key ingredients for maximizing its impact throughout the duration and after the completion of the project:

- The **active involvement** of all relevant POIESIS stakeholders in research activities. POIESIS aims for the involvement to be both creative and fruitful for stakeholders, as well as for POIESIS beneficiaries. The variety of types of empirical studies and participatory research actions will be considered successful as long as this mutual benefit will have been met.
- The **development of outputs** that will be relevant to contexts both in academia and the chains of mediation. To maximise impact, it is crucial that the POIESIS research findings and outcomes are easily accessible and have the capacity to be relevant in a wide range of contexts. This will define POIESIS' success in regard to the diffusion and the overall impact of the project's outputs.
- **Commitment to open-access publishing, and widespread availability** of POIESIS project results, retrieved data and project outputs. POIESIS is dedicated to Open Science. The project's results and outputs will be openly accessible not only for moral and epistemic reasons, but also in order to maximise their impact through their widespread diffusion to the public and the scientific community.
- **Continued focus on stakeholder engagement throughout** the project is a key aspect of POIESIS' dissemination and exploitation

strategy. We expect that our efforts to engage stakeholders from the start and throughout the duration of the project will result in increased awareness of the potential of responsible Open Science and research integrity practices, as well as it will contribute to increased interest in POIESIS' results, as our proposed solutions will be tailored to stakeholders' specific needs. Stakeholder involvement and mutual learning among key stakeholders, with the substantial involvement of the country co-investigators, bears the potential to provide sustainable opportunities for project uptake and application also after project termination.

The goals above underline the importance for POIESIS to develop and implement a robust and ambitious plan, in order to 1) **recruit and engage** core stakeholders to become involved in POIESIS' research activities in the seven partner countries, 2) widely **disseminate and communicate** POIESIS' activities, research findings and outputs, 3) **optimize uptake and exploitation** of POIESIS' recommendations to boost the sustainability of POIESIS' outcomes.

1.3 About this Deliverable

This report presents the update of the DEPC of POIESIS that was submitted in M4 of the project. This report is an augmented version of D4.2, based on the interactions with various stakeholders that took place within the first 22 months of POIESIS, in the context of dissemination and communication, as well as in the context of the engagement procedures and empirical data collection studies that were successfully implemented.

1.4 List of Abbreviations

AU	Aarhus University
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CSIC	Agencia estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas
DEPC	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan including Communication activities
DoA	Description of Action
iRECS	improving Research Ethics Expertise and Competencies to Ensure Reliability and Trust in Science
ISCTE	Instituto Universitario de Lisboa
KER	Key Exploitable Results

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSE	London School of Economics and political science
MA	Mediating Actors
NGO	Non Governmental Organisation
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
OS	Open Science
R&I	Research & Innovation
Res.	Researchers
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RI	Research Integrity
RIO	Research Integrity Officers
RPM	Research Policy Makers
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SOPs4RI	Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity
WiD	Wissenschaft im Dialog
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop

2 Plan for dissemination activities

POIESIS' approach to dissemination is to maximise impact by involving key stakeholders in its empirical programme, so that they are also enabled and motivated to carry on the widespread use of the results in their own interest. POIESIS' **dissemination** activities will **target seven different groups of stakeholders (Mediating Actors, Researchers, Research Leaders and Managers, Research Integrity Officers, Research Policy Makers, Research Funding Organizations and the General Public)**, being instrumental to achieve a high impact.

WP4 has developed a repository that includes more than 150 entities (Institutions/Networks) and more than 1000 individuals that are potential stakeholders for recruitment from the 7 countries of the consortium members, as well as from international and European organisations and networks. These institutions have been retrieved from the followers of the Social Media channels of the project SOPs4RI (coordinated by AU) that has achieved significant attention, with more than 1600 followers in Twitter. Given the topic relatedness of the SOPs4RI and POIESIS projects, a considerable overlap in project stakeholders is to be expected. However, additional stakeholders for the POIESIS project may emerge and the project will therefore continuously try to expand its dissemination network.

These entities are listed in the Annex of this report. While drafting this table, WP4 partners took also into account the fields of interests of these institutions (in order to fit with the respective interests of POIESIS), their general status and impact on society and their geographic proximity with the operational base of the 7 POIESIS partners. This repository includes 6 potential entities from Denmark, 13 from France, 37 from Germany, 5 from Greece, 8 from Portugal, 16 from Spain and 49 from the UK (see Figure 1).

Entities mapped per Country of Origin

Figure 1: Pie chart depicting the breakdown of the entities found from the mapping per country (the numbers in the pie chart represent percentages).

Bearing in mind that a network could have multiple roles, there are 42 potential entities whose role are best described as mediating actors, 44 as research policy makers, 86 as research performing organisations (RPOs), 10 as research funding organisations (RFOs), 6 as researcher’s groups and 2 as research integrity offices (see Figure 2). Those stakeholders are not only to be used for POIEISIS dissemination strategy, but also for communication and exploitation purposes. The development of this network will be an ever-changing procedure and it will be continuously expanding with the contribution of all the POIEISIS partners, through their established networks.

Figure 2: Pie chart depicting the breakdown of the entities found from the mapping with regard to their main role as stakeholders (the numbers in the pie chart represent percentages).

As it is also depicted on the Table below (Table 1), POIEISIS should engage the aforementioned stakeholders in a variety of ways: a) with a series of co-creation events such as Expert interviews, Survey Experiments, Focus Groups, Open Deliberative Roundtable Workshops, b) with oral and poster presentations in Conferences, c) the Newsfeed of our website, d) via the projects’ Social Media channels on LinkedIn and Twitter and e) through the POIEISIS outputs which will be communicated via its deliverables and publications.

Engaging these potential stakeholders comes as a necessary addition to the strong links that all POIEISIS consortium members have established, thanks to existing structures of collaboration and activities during the preparation and the first months of the project. An overview of the target stakeholders, the purpose for dissemination

and the specific channels and tools for dissemination are presented in Table 1, which is an augmented/updated version of the relevant table from the proposal text, while the aforementioned institutions are presented in the table at the Annex.

Table 1: POIESIS dissemination strategy

Target stakeholders	Purpose of dissemination	Main channels of dissemination	Tools of dissemination
Mediating actors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science journalists (e.g. <i>Research Fortnight</i>, <i>Significance Magazine</i>) • Scientific blogs (e.g. <i>Conversation</i>, <i>LSE Impact blog</i>, <i>Scholarly Kitchen</i>) • Influential bloggers • Science communication officers • Science public events organizers (e.g., <i>Researcher's Nights</i>, <i>Technology Museums</i>) • Technology Assessment networks (e.g. <i>TechAssessment</i>, <i>Global TA</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events - Promote POIESIS' results - Raise awareness of POIESIS' findings 	Co-creation events	Town Hall meetings, Survey experiment, Focus groups, Open deliberative roundtable WS
		Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
Researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In academia (<i>faculty members</i>) • In RPOs (Publicly funded and private Universities and Research institutes) • In industry (<i>BGI</i>, <i>Novozymes</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events - Promote POIESIS' results 	Co-creation events	Experts WSs, Public deliberation, Expert interviews, Survey experiment, Focus groups, Open deliberative roundtable WS
		Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS outputs	Deliverables, Peer reviewed publications
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts

Research leaders and managers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learned societies (e.g. the GUILD, ALLEA) • National Academies of Science • Members of RPO administration bodies • RPO associations (e.g. AEESSME, ARRIGE, Formindep) • RFO associations (Science Europe) • Research administrators associations (e.g. EARMA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events - Promote POIESIS' results - Promote uptake of POIESIS' results 	Co-creation events	Experts WSS, Public deliberation, Expert interviews, Survey experiment, Focus groups, Open deliberative roundtable WS
		Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
Research Integrity Officers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks of RIOs (e.g. members of UKRIO, ENRIO, Ofis) • World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events - Promote POIESIS' results - Promote uptake of POIESIS' results 	Co-creation events	Experts Workshops, Public deliberation, Expert interviews, Survey experiment, Focus groups, Open deliberative roundtable WS
		Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
Research policy makers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Parliament • Members of STOA • EC officials • Members of CEI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events - Promote uptake of POIESIS' results 	Co-creation events	Public deliberation, Open deliberative roundtable WS
		Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
RFOs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RFO associations (Science Europe, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruiting in engagement events 	Co-creation events	Public deliberation, Open deliberative roundtable WS

<i>Siemens, Orange [for the cases these entities act as funding bodies]</i>	- Promote uptake of POIESIS' results	Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
The general public <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science communities • Citizen Science Associations (e.g. ECSA, EUSEA) • CSOs (<i>Sense About Science, Science for Change</i>) • Minority groups • User communities • Individual lay people 	- Recruiting in engagement events - Promote POIESIS' results	Co-creation events	Public deliberation, Survey experiment
		POIESIS website	Newsfeed
		POIESIS social media	Tweets, Re-tweets, LinkedIn posts

3 Plan for Exploitation Activities

The **overarching exploitation objective** of POIESIS is the public availability of evidence-based recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research. POIESIS aims to inform with its outputs not only the scientific community, but also a wider number of societal actors, including all the target groups of the project. The project's outputs will benefit the target groups by setting new standards in terms of communicating with the public, performing and communicating research, decision-making, etc. Among the POIESIS main goals is that all project stakeholders and participants will contribute to the dissemination of the project's recommendations and outputs, since POIESIS aspires to combine its communication, dissemination and exploitation operations.

Table 2 presents the exploitation routes through which the respective targeted groups will benefit from POIESIS' expected Key Exploitable Result (KER), i.e. the POIESIS recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research.

Table 2: Different exploitation routes to target groups of POIESIS KER.

Target groups	Exploitation route
<p>Mediating Actors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science journalists (e.g. <i>Research Fortnight</i>, <i>Significance Magazine</i>) • Scientific blogs (e.g. <i>Conversation</i>, <i>LSE Impact blog</i>, <i>Scholarly Kitchen</i>) • Influential bloggers • Science communication officers • Science public events organizers (e.g., <i>Researcher's Nights</i>, <i>Technology Museums</i>) • Technology Assessment networks (e.g. <i>TechAssessment</i>, <i>Global TA</i>) 	<p>New standards (e.g. augment current training of science journalists or revise the code of conduct for science journalists) in communication with the public</p> <p>New standards (e.g. augment current training on RI/OS or revise institutional code of conduct for RI/OS) and procedures in performing research (e.g. augment current standard operating procedures in all stages of research, from laboratory practices to communication with the public)</p> <p>New standards for decision-making with regard to communicating research by researchers and RPOs (from inception to market placing)</p> <p>New standards with regard to RI and more prevalent co-creation processes for RPOs to receive funding</p>
<p>Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In academia (<i>faculty members</i>) • In RPOs (Publicly funded and private Universities and Research institutes) • In industry (<i>BGI</i>, <i>Novozymes</i>) 	
<p>Research leaders and managers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learned societies (e.g. <i>the GUILD</i>, <i>ALLEA</i>) • National Academies of Science • Members of RPO administration bodies • RPO associations (e.g. <i>AEESME</i>, <i>ARRIGE</i>, <i>Formindep</i>) • RFO associations (<i>Science Europe</i>) • Research administrators associations (e.g. <i>EARMA</i>) 	
<p>Research Integrity Officers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks of RIOs (e.g. <i>members of UKRIO</i>, <i>ENRIO</i>, <i>Ofis</i>) • World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation 	
<p>Research policy makers and RFOs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA) • European Parliament • EC officials • Members of CEI • RFO associations and national RFOs 	

<p>The general public</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science communities • Citizen Science Associations (e.g. <i>ECSA, EUSEA</i>) • CSOs (<i>Sense About Science, Science for Change</i>) • Minority groups • User communities • Individual lay people 	<p>New identified contexts for contribution to the co-creation of R&I contents</p>
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4 Plan for communication activities

Through targeted and easily accessible **communication activities** POIESIS will ensure that interested individuals and organisations are aware of POIESIS' progress and findings. These activities are important to increase visibility of the project, gain awareness, and reach a wide range of stakeholders. As part of WP4, the consortium will ensure timely and clear communication of project results to all relevant stakeholder groups (Table 3). In each communication channel there is a list of the stakeholders that are mainly going to be targeted in each case. This does not mean that other stakeholders that are not listed will not be informed by these specific channels. However, the main targets of communication will define the language that is going to be used; e.g. press releases will mainly target lay people, so the language to be used will be as simple as possible, while LinkedIn will mainly target our peers, so the language will be more technical, however not using very sophisticated jargon.

All POIESIS partners have extensive experience in online and offline communication and will use this asset to communicate with potential and existing stakeholders. The pre-existence of communication accounts (organisational and individual) and established networks are already providing smooth and wide-reaching announcements for the project's outputs. Table 4 presents a list of **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that must be reached, to consider the communication activities successful.

Over the length of the first 2 years of POIESIS, the projects' partners participated in several dissemination and communication activities; POIESIS research questions and objectives, the progress of its findings were presented on conferences and events across the consortium countries and beyond. Those included presentations at the 6th STS Nordic Conference (AU), at the Forum Wissenschaftskommunikation 2023 (WiD), at the XII SOPCOM Congress and 12th SciComPT Congress (CIES-Iscte). Most notably POIESIS took part at the OPERAS Trust On 2024 Event concerning how to address

misinformation and promote trust. POIESIS chaired the Science Track sessions along with sisters' projects IANUS, VERITY, and COALESCE. All projects will also be present in reporting the results from the workshop at the UN Summit of the Future 2024 in September, 2024. The early findings of POIESIS were also presented by coordinator Tine Ravn (AU) at the 8th World Conference on Research Integrity that took place in Athens (2-5 June 2024).

Additionally, articles have already been or are planned to be published regarding POIESIS objectives and findings. A consortium member affiliated with NTUA, wrote an article at the early stages of the project about POIESIS in a Greek magazine of science communication that is being circulated as an inset with a Greek newspaper of national circulation. POIESIS was also included in a REA article that presents a brief overview of the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects revolving around Research for Peace, Sustainable Development and Trust In Science. Publications regarding POIESIS findings will be initiated within the next months. A book proposal we have submitted along with our sister projects VERITY and IANUS has been accepted by Springer Nature. The book will be published as an open access book.

This partnership with VERITY and IANUS, two projects with relevant research topics and questions, is an important asset for POIESIS' communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts. It extends on the project's communication channels, on exchanging valuable information, on discussing research methods and results, and on joint publication efforts to maximize the impact of our research. As already noted, the projects organised and participated in a joint symposium on the "Implications of research integrity for public trust in academic research" on WCRI 2024 and co-chaired a science track at the OPERAS event.

Regarding the KPIs related to Social Media, POIESIS comfortably exceeding the targets that were set at the beginning of the project, in terms of website visitors and followers, on both of our social media channels (*KPIs overall progress is shown in red bold text in parentheses*). Additional efforts should be made to exploit this great asset by increasing the number of posts both on our website and our social media channels over the last year of POIESIS. This will be facilitated by POIESIS's progress in collecting empirical evidence, primarily through the planned studies, most of which took place during the second year. As a result, the consortium has a solid base of findings to disseminate.

Table 3: POIESIS communication channels with the main targeted stakeholders per channel.

<p>Branding: NTUA has developed a brand identity for the POIESIS website, deliverables, oral presentation and poster templates after consultation with the coordinators. The branding is presented in D4.3. POIESIS appealing brand identity consists of a logo, colour set and choice of typography will be utilized in all types of communication activities.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Lay people, mediating actors</p>	
<p>Website: The POIESIS website is under preparation and will be launched on schedule (Month 4), in order to provide up-to-date information on the project, partners, progress, goals, events and outputs (e.g. deliverables and peer reviewed publications). It is based on the POIESIS branding, colours and aesthetics.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Policy makers, RIOs</p>	
<p>Social media: Social media are instrumental in reaching all relevant stakeholders. POIESIS social media channels (LinkedIn and Twitter) are active since the beginning of the project and are already actively communicating POIESIS' progress, already exceeding in some terms-as mentioned before- the KPIs for POIESIS Year 1, that were set at the beginning of the project.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Lay people, Mediating actors (via Twitter), Researchers (LinkedIn)</p>	
<p>Conferences: POIESIS consortium members are participating in conferences and interacting with experts in the field of RI, RRI and OS, exchanging valuable experiences with relevant stakeholders. This will help greatly in gaining experience, recruiting and communicating POIESIS' progress.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Researchers, RFOs</p>	
<p>Workshops: POIESIS partners are actively participating in other relevant running EU-funded projects (H2020 and HE), workshops/events and cluster events organised by the EC. This is also useful for recruiting stakeholders, as well as promoting POIESIS activities.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Researchers, Policy makers, RFOs, RIOs</p>	
<p>Public outreach events: POIESIS partners are also participating in open lectures in science museums, participate in researcher's night events and in science communication events, building chains of mediation with a plethora of stakeholders.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Lay people</p>	
<p>Press releases: Press releases, targeting newspapers with national circulation written in national languages, in all the 7 partner countries will boost the project's communication of the latest findings at a national scale. POIESIS partners have rich experience in promoting similar projects this way in the recent past, and are aware of how crucial this is in order to achieve our communication goals.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Lay people, Mediating actors</p>	
<p>Printed material: Dissemination materials such as newsletters and brochures will be produced to inform all relevant stakeholders. Project progress and relevant updates from outside POIESIS will also be presented via the POIESIS website and its other communication channels.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: RFOs, RIOs, Researchers</p>	
<p>Scientific publications: Publications in leading peer reviewed field journals related to RI, research policy, and PUS (e.g. Research Integrity and Peer Review, Science and Engineering Ethics, Research Policy, Public Understanding of Science, Science and Public Policy, Science Communication). This is also crucial for promoting POIESIS' progress, results and outcomes to the wider scientific community.</p> <p>Targeted stakeholders: Researchers</p>	

Table 4: KPIs for POIESIS' communication activities (current progress is shown in red)

Channel	Tool	Indicator	M12	M24	M36
Website	Newsfeed	Number	15	30 (30)	60
	E-newsletters	Number	2	4 (3)	6
	Visits	Visits	250	700 (3400)	2500
Social media	Twitter	followers/tweets re-tweets/likes	100/10 100/50	300 (725) / 20 (33) 300 (1086) / 200 (487)	1000/500 500/500
	LinkedIn	followers/posts	40/20	100 (589) / 40 (33)	200/80
Scientific conferences	Oral/poster presentations	participations	4	8 (6)	12

5 Deviations from DoA

There are no deviations from DoA.

6 Annex

The following table lists POIESIS' potential dissemination targets.

No.	Name of the organisation	Town	Country	Organisation Type
1	EARMA	Brussels	Belgium / European	RPM
2	European Research Council (ERE)	Brussels	Belgium / European	RPM
3	Science Europe	Brussels	Belgium / European	RPM, MA
4	STOA Panel	Brussels	Belgium / European	RPM
5	The Guild	Brussels	Belgium / European	RPO, MA, RPM
6	BGI	Copenhagen	Denmark	RPO, RPM
7	CAS Research Team	Aarhus	Denmark	RPO
8	CFA Research Policy	Aarhus	Denmark	RPO
9	Danish Board of Technology	Hvidovre	Denmark	RPM, RPO
10	DTU - Technical university of Denmark	Kongens, Lyngby	Denmark	RPO
11	Novozymes	Bagsværd	Denmark	RFO, MA
12	ARRIGE	Paris	France	RPO

13	CEA Paris-Saclay	Ile de France	France	RPO
14	CorTexT platform	Paris	France	MA
15	Formindep		France	RPO
16	ISE (Initiative for Science in Europe)	Strasbourg	France	MA
17	Libraries of the University of Lille	Lille	France	RPO, MA
18	Office français de l'intégrité scientifique (Ofis)	Paris	France	RIO
19	Orange	Paris	France	RFO
20	ReiTheR	Rennes	France	RPO
21	rogueESR	Network	France	RPM
22	Sorbonne Université	Paris	France	RPO
23	Tree of Science	Paris	France	RPO
24	Université de Versailles Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines	Paris	France	RPO
25	ACEEU	Muenster	Germany	RPM
26	BAM	Berlin	Germany	RPO, RPM
27	BASF	Ludwigshafen	Germany	RPO, RFO
28	BIH QUEST Centre	Berlin	Germany	RPO, RPM
29	Consortium of European Research Libraries	Goettingen	Germany	RPO
30	Das Gen-ethische Netzwerk	Berlin	Germany	RPM
31	Deutscher Ethikrat	Berlin	Germany	RPM
32	EA European Academy	Bad Neuenahr-Ahrweiler	Germany	RPO, MA, RPM
33	Ecological Research Network	Berlin	Germany	RPO, RPM
34	Einstein Foundation	Berlin	Germany	RPO
35	EMDESK. Project & Work Management Solution	Erfurt	Germany	MA
36	European Citizen Science Association	Berlin	Germany	MA, RPO, RFO
37	Fraunhofer IESE	Kaiserslautern	Germany	RPO
38	Fraunhofer Institute for Ceramic Technologies and Systems	Dresden	Germany	RPO
39	Fraunhofer Institute for High Frequency Physics and Radar Techniques FHR	Fraunhofer	Germany	RPO
40	German Reproducibility Network		Germany	Res.
41	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions	Koln	Germany	MA
42	IWM - Fraunhofer Institute for Mechanics of Materials	Freiburg	Germany	RPO

43	KIT ARRTI	Karlsruhe	Germany	RPO
44	KIT Karlsruhe	Karlsruhe	Germany	RPO
45	Meta - Research Innovation Centre	Berlin	Germany	Res.
46	Neckel Lab	Tuebingen	Germany	Res.
47	Openbioprojects.net	Karlsruhe	Germany	MA
48	Researcher Mental Health Observatory	Hannover	Germany	RPO
49	Siemens	Munich	Germany	RFO
50	Takeda Germany	Berlin	Germany	RFO
51	TechAssessment	Karlsruhe	Germany	RPO
52	Technical University Munich	Munich	Germany	RPO
53	Technische Universität Dresden	Dresden	Germany	RPO
54	United Nations University-FLORES	Dresden	Germany	RPO
55	YVORI	Bochum	Germany	RPO
56	ALLEA	Berlin	Germany	RPO, MA, RPM
57	EARTHnet	Athens	Greece	RPO
58	General Secretariat of Research and Technology	Athens	Greece	RPM
59	Hellenic General Council of Libraries	Patras	Greece	RPM, MA
60	PREGO project	Heraklion	Greece	RPO
61	University of Athens - European Histamine Research Society	Athens	Greece	RPO
62	AMBER-Biometrics	Europe	International	RPO
63	Citizen Science Association	USA	International	RPM
64	DOAJ	Global	International	MA, RPM
65	Epidemics Ethics	Global	International	MA, RPM
66	EUSEA - European Science Engagement Association	International	International	MA
67	GoEQIPD	International	International	MA, RPO
68	HBP & Society	International	International	
69	Inno4cov19	International	International	H2020
70	OpenAIRE	International	Europe	MA, RPM
71	QualAItY Engagement	International	International	H2020
72	Quantitative Science Studies	International	International	MA
73	REWARD Alliance	International	International	RPO, RPM
74	RIPR Journal	International	International	MA, RPM
75	SDG Watch Europe	International	International	RPM, NGOs

76	Stick to Science	International	International	RPM
77	Voice of Researchers	Europe	International	MA, RPM
78	Women in Copernicus	International	International	MA, RPM
79	D.RibeiroLab - Virus Host-Cell Interactions	Aveiro	Portugal	RPO
80	FLOWer Lab of CFE AND Uni of Coimbra	Coimbra	Portugal	RPO
81	GHTM - Global Health & Tropical Medicine - NOVA	Lisbon	Portugal	RPO
82	Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering	Porto	Portugal	RPO
83	polli.NET	Network	Portugal	RPM
84	Revista Voz do Campo	Castelo Branco	Portugal	MA
85	University of Aveiro	Aveiro	Portugal	RPO
86	EpiViral	Aveiro, Frankfurt	Portugal, Germany	RPO
87	ADE UPV	Valencia	Spain	RPO
88	AEESME	Madrid	Spain	MA, RPM
89	BETA Tech Center	Vic	Spain	RPO
90	Cátedra UNESCO de Comunicación (InCom-UAB)	Barcelona	Spain	RPO
91	CVC_UAB	Barcelona	Spain	RPO
92	GloCee - Global Change Ecology & Evolution	Madrid	Spain	RPO
93	IIS-FJD Translational Bioinformatics Lab	Madrid	Spain	RPO
94	IK4-Tekniker	Eibar	Spain	RPO
95	Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón	Zaragoza	Spain	RPO
96	JNALS	Caceres	Spain	MA
97	Science For Change	Barcelona	Spain	RPO, RPM
98	Telefonica	Madrid	Spain	RFO
99	UNED Faculty of Philosophy	Madrid	Spain	RPO
100	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Barcelona	Spain	RPO
101	Universitat Politècnica de Madrid	Madrid	Spain	RPO
102	UPF Medicine and Life Sciences	Barcelona	Spain	RPO
103	(EDMA) European Dissemination Media Agency	London	UK	RPM
104	Cambridge Nanomaterials Technology Ltd	Cambridge	UK	RPO
105	CDT in Speech and Language Technologies	Sheffield	UK	RPO
106	Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation		UK	RPM
107	Cochrane UK	Oxford	UK	RPO

108	Consilium Scientific	London	UK	RPO, RPM
109	Consortium of European Research Libraries	Oxford	UK	RPO
110	CrowdHelix	London	UK	MA
111	Dimensions		UK	MA
112	EASE	London	UK	MA
113	ECPR Knowledge		UK	RPM, MA
114	Edinburgh Genome Foundry	Edinburgh	UK	RPO
115	Edinburgh ReproducibiliTea	Edinburgh	UK	Res.
116	EQUATOR Network	Oxford	UK	RPO, RPM
117	Experimental Results	Cambridge	UK	MA
118	Figshare	London	UK	DATA
119	FLA	Loughborough	UK	RPO
120	Goldbeck Consulting	Cambridge	UK	MA
121	Institute of Physics		UK	MA, RPM
122	King's College London	London	UK	RPO
123	Lancaster University	Lancaster	UK	RPO
124	LSE Data Science Institute	London	UK	RPO
125	LSE Psychological & Behavioural Science	London	UK	RPO
126	Manchester Institute of Innovation Research	Manchester	UK	RPO
127	Morein Lab	Cambridge	UK	RPO
128	National Physical Laboratory	Teddington	UK	RPO
129	Octo Telematics	London	UK	RFO, MA
130	Old Age Psychiatry Kings College	London	UK	RPO
131	Open Data Institute	London	UK	RPM
132	Oxitec	Oxfordshire	UK	RPM, MA
133	PLOS Biology	Cambridge	UK	MA
134	ReproducibiliTea Manchester	Manchester	UK	Res.
135	Research Aether	Cheshire	UK	MA
136	Research Fortnight	London	UK	MA
137	Rethinking Research Ethics	Westminster, Manchester	UK	RPO, MA
138	Significance Magazine		UK	MA
139	Sky	London	UK	RFO
140	The Alan Turing Institute	London	UK	RPO, RPM
141	Transforming Evidence	London	UK	MA, RPO
142	TranspariMED	Bristol	UK	MA, RPO
143	UK Government Social Media Research Group	London	UK	RPO, RPM
144	UK Reproducibility Network		UK	Res.
145	UK Research Integrity Office	Croydon (London)	UK	RIO

146	University of Birmingham	Birmingham	UK	RPO
147	University of Oxford	Oxford	UK	RPO
148	University of York	York	UK	RPO
149	UofGlasgow Research Integrity	Glasgow	UK	RPO
150	UOSH - University of Sheffield - Department of computer science	Sheffield	UK	RPO
151	Voice of Young Science	London	UK	MA
152	Stakeholder Forum	International	USA (Global)	RPM, NGO